

РАЗДЕЛ. ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫЕ НАУКИ

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7741832>

UDK 168.521

**FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM OF NORMAL
SEPARATION-TYPE FRACTURE**

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Annotation: An approach to solving the problems of fracture mechanics at the scale level of continuum mechanics is proposed. For an elementary volume element, within the framework of this approach, the onset of the moment of formation of new material surfaces is considered. A statement and a method for solving a particular problem of fracture mechanics are proposed.

Keywords: characteristic size, boundary integral equation, linear elasticity, fracture mechanics, approach, continuum mechanics

**ПОСТАНОВКА ЗАДАЧИ О НОРМАЛЬНОМ РАЗРЫВЕ
ОТРЫВНОГО ТИПА**

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Аннотация: Предлагается подход к решению задач механики разрушения на масштабном уровне механики сплошной среды. Для элементарного элемента объема в рамках этого подхода рассматривается наступление момента образования новых поверхностей материала. Предложены постановка и метод решения частной задачи механики разрушения.

Ключевые слова: характерный размер, граничное интегральное уравнение, линейная упругость, механика разрушения, подход, механика сплошной среды

In the process of external, monotonous up to a certain moment, impacts on a solid, its material goes through the stages of reversible (elastic), irreversible equilibrium (elastic-plastic) deformation and, finally, the stage of destruction. The least studied, but also the most important from the applied point of view, is the destruction stage. The essential difference of this stage from the previous ones is that if elastic and inelastic deformation can cover the entire material of the body, in particular, the deformed state can be homogeneous, then the destruction process, as a rule, is localized in thin layers. The complexity of describing such processes is associated with the uncertainty of the very concept of «fracture».

Historically, there have been two directions for describing destruction. The first considers the onset of the limiting state in the vicinity of the continuum point for bodies without initial cuts [1]. In this case, the moment of onset of a critical state in the vicinity of a material point is determined and the further evolution of destruction, in particular, the process of formation of new material surfaces, is not considered. The second direction is the determination of the conditions for the beginning of the movement of a cut in the body, which is assumed to be either mathematical (the theory of cracks) [6] or physical, having a certain characteristic size [7-10]. For a mathematical cut, the process of surface formation is not associated with the destruction of the material in the sense of using strength criteria. As a condition for the beginning of the advance of the discontinuity surface, the Griffith criterion is taken in the energy or force versions. In [2-5], it is proposed to consider destruction as a thermomechanical process, and estimates of the corresponding scale level are given through the known mechanical characteristics of the medium.

As an example of solving the separation problem at the scale level of fulfillment of continuum mechanics hypotheses, let us consider the conditions for the beginning of the advancement of a physical cut (interaction layer) [2] in a linearly elastic plane according to the scheme shown in Fig. 1, corresponding to a normal separation type failure.

In contrast to the formulation of the problem [2], along with the stress $\sigma_{11}(x_2)$, we take into account the stress $\sigma_{22}(x_2)$, due to the presence of tangential stresses $\sigma_{21}(x_2)$ along the boundary with the layer. Let us

emphasize that the uniformity of the stress-deformed state in the layer is postulated in the direction orthogonal to the separation surface (the Ox_2x_3 plane).

Figure 1 – Scheme of plane separation

We believe that the relationship between stresses and strains outside the interaction layer is described by the relations of the linear theory of elasticity for the case of plane deformation. Due to the symmetry of the problem, we consider only the upper half-plane ($x_1 \geq \delta_0/2$) (Fig. 2), and the action of the layer is equivalent to the load on the half-plane $\vec{q}(x) = -(\tilde{\sigma}_{11}\vec{e}_1 + \tilde{\sigma}_{21}\vec{e}_2)$ (here and below, $x \equiv x_2/\delta_0$ – dimensionless coordinate, $\tilde{\sigma}_{ij} = \sigma_{ij} \cdot \beta$ $i, j = 1, 2$ – dimensionless stresses, $\beta = \frac{2(1-\nu^2)}{\pi E}$ – material parameter, E – modulus of elasticity, ν – Poisson’s ratio).

Figure 2 – Plane loading scheme

The relationship between the stress $\tilde{\sigma}_{22}$ in the interaction layer and the stress $\tilde{\sigma}_{21}$ along the layer boundary can be obtained from the equilibrium condition of the layer element in the form

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\sigma}_{22}}{\partial x} = -2\tilde{\sigma}_{21}. \tag{1}$$

Based on the solution of the Flaman problem, the distribution of displacements of the points of the boundary of the half-plane under the action of the loads shown in Fig. 2 has the form

$$\tilde{u}_1(x) = -\tilde{P} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{x+a}{L+a}\right) + \int_0^L \tilde{\sigma}_{11}(\xi) \cdot \ln\left(\frac{|x-\xi|}{L-\xi}\right) d\xi, \quad (2)$$

$$\tilde{u}_2(x) = \int_0^L \tilde{\sigma}_{21}(\xi) \cdot \ln\left(\frac{|x-\xi|}{L-\xi}\right) d\xi, \quad (3)$$

where $\tilde{u}_i = u_i/\delta_0$, $i, j = 1, 2$ are dimensionless displacements; $\tilde{P} = P\beta/\delta_0$ is the dimensionless force per unit of thickness; L is a remote point with zero displacement; L is the distance from the origin to L .

We write the displacements in the left-hand sides of (2) and (3) through the corresponding principal deformations of the interaction layer, taking into account the hypothesis of uniformity of the stress-deformed state over the layer thickness

$$\tilde{u}_1(x) = \varepsilon_{11}(x)/2, \quad (4)$$

$$\tilde{u}_2(x) = \int_L^x \frac{\varepsilon_{22}(x)}{2} dx. \quad (5)$$

We find the expression for the principal strains in terms of the corresponding stresses from Hooke's law

$$\varepsilon_{11} = \tilde{A}\tilde{\sigma}_{11} - \tilde{B}\tilde{\sigma}_{22}, \quad (6)$$

$$\varepsilon_{22} = \tilde{A}\tilde{\sigma}_{22} - \tilde{B}\tilde{\sigma}_{11}, \quad (7)$$

where $\tilde{A} = \frac{\pi}{2}$, $\tilde{B} = \frac{\nu\pi}{2(1-\nu)}$ are dimensionless constants.

Thus, taking into account (4), (6), we represent the boundary integral equation (2) in the following form

$$\frac{1}{2}(\tilde{A}\tilde{\sigma}_{11} - \tilde{B}\tilde{\sigma}_{22}) = -\tilde{P} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{x+a}{L+a}\right) + \int_0^L \tilde{\sigma}_{11}(\xi) \cdot \ln\left(\frac{|x-\xi|}{L-\xi}\right) d\xi. \quad (8)$$

Let us differentiate expression (3) with respect to x

$$\varepsilon_{22} = \frac{d\tilde{u}_2}{dx} = \int_0^L \tilde{\sigma}_{12}(\xi) \frac{1}{x-\xi} d\xi. \quad (9)$$

We substitute expression (7) into formula (9), as a result we obtain

$$\tilde{A}\tilde{\sigma}_{22} - \tilde{B}\tilde{\sigma}_{11} = \int_0^L \tilde{\sigma}_{21}(\xi) \frac{1}{x-\xi} d\xi. \quad (10)$$

The absence of stresses $\tilde{\sigma}_{22}$ at the point O and the condition of stress decay at infinity leads to the following boundary condition

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{22}|_{x=0} = 0. \quad (11)$$

Thus, we have a system of integral equations (8), (10) supplemented by relation (1). Let us rewrite the resulting system of integro-differential equations in the form:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}(\tilde{A}\tilde{\sigma}_{11} - \tilde{B}\tilde{\sigma}_{22}) = -\tilde{P} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{x+a}{L+a}\right) + \int_0^L \tilde{\sigma}_{11}(\xi) \cdot \ln\left(\frac{|x-\xi|}{L-\xi}\right) d\xi \\ \tilde{A}\tilde{\sigma}_{22} - \tilde{B}\tilde{\sigma}_{11} = \int_0^L \tilde{\sigma}_{21}(\xi) \frac{1}{x-\xi} d\xi \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{\sigma}_{22}}{\partial x} = -2\tilde{\sigma}_{21} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

The result of solving system (12) is to find the stress field $\tilde{\sigma}_{11}$ and $\tilde{\sigma}_{22}$, as well as shear stresses along the boundary with the layer $-\tilde{\sigma}_{21}$ under the condition of stress decay at infinity: $\tilde{\sigma}_{11}|_{x=L} = \tilde{\sigma}_{21}|_{x=L} = \tilde{\sigma}_{22}|_{x=L} = 0$.

To solve the problem in the framework of the discrete model, we divide the boundary of the half-plane OL into N boundary elements [8]. We consider that each boundary element is characterized by a constant (element average) stress value $\tilde{\sigma}_{ii}^{(k)}$, where $k = \overline{1 \dots N}$, $i = 1, 2$.

Let us construct discrete expressions for integral operators in the equations of system (12)

$$\int_0^L \tilde{\sigma}_{11}(\xi) \ln\left(\frac{|x-\xi|}{L-\xi}\right) d\xi = \sum_{k=1}^N \tilde{\sigma}_{11}^{(k)} \cdot \int_{\xi_k}^{\xi_{k+1}} \ln\left(\frac{|x_j-\xi|}{L-\xi}\right) d\xi, \quad (13)$$

$$\int_0^L \tilde{\sigma}_{21}(\xi) \cdot \frac{1}{x-\xi} d\xi = \sum_{k=1}^N \tilde{\sigma}_{21}^{(k)} \cdot \int_{\xi_k}^{\xi_{k+1}} \frac{1}{x_j-\xi} d\xi. \quad (14)$$

Using the condition of constant stress $\tilde{\sigma}_{21}^{(j)}$ and the derivative $\frac{d^j \tilde{\sigma}_{22}}{dx}$, relation (1) will take the following form

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{21}^{(j)} = -\frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{22}^{(j)} - \tilde{\sigma}_{22}^{(j-1)}}{2}. \quad (15)$$

Thus, system (12) is reduced to the following system of linear algebraic equations for $\tilde{\sigma}_{11}^{(k)}$, $\tilde{\sigma}_{21}^{(k)}$ and $\tilde{\sigma}_{22}^{(k)}$

Таким образом, система (12) сводится к следующей системе линейных алгебраических уравнений относительно $\tilde{\sigma}_{11}^{(k)}$, $\tilde{\sigma}_{21}^{(k)}$ и $\tilde{\sigma}_{22}^{(k)}$

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\tilde{A}}{2}\tilde{\sigma}_{11}^{(j)} - \frac{\tilde{B}}{2}\tilde{\sigma}_{22}^{(j)} = -\tilde{P}^{(j)} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{x_j+a}{L+a}\right) + \sum_{k=1}^N \tilde{\sigma}_{11}^{(k)} \cdot \int_{\xi_k}^{\xi_{k+1}} \ln\left(\frac{x_j-\xi}{L-\xi}\right) d\xi, \\ \tilde{A}\tilde{\sigma}_{22}^{(j)} - \tilde{B}\tilde{\sigma}_{11}^{(j)} = \sum_{k=1}^N \tilde{\sigma}_{21}^{(k)} \cdot \int_{\xi_k}^{\xi_{k+1}} \frac{1}{x_j-\xi} d\xi, \\ \tilde{\sigma}_{22}^{(j)} = -\frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{22}^{(j)} - \tilde{\sigma}_{22}^{(j-1)}}{2}. \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Poisson's ratio practically does not affect the stress distribution σ_{11} , but has a significant effect on the stress σ_{22} . The dependence obtained shows that the stress of σ_{22} for the physical section corresponds to the

stress of σ_{11} and can play a significant role in the formation of the plastic zone preceding the beginning of separation. In addition, the ratio $\frac{\sigma_{22}}{\sigma_{11}}$ for the discrete model under consideration depends significantly on the Poisson's ratio.

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Поступила в редакцию 05.02.2023

Принята к публикации 23.02.2023

Для цитирования:

Le Thi Hong Van, Tran Minh Quang Formulation of the problem of normal separation-type fracture // Инновационные научные исследования. 2023. № 2-3(26). С. 4-10. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>